

A DSEL for Computational Category Theory

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Abstract Computational category theory is a branch of computer science devoted to the study of algorithms which can be stated in terms of category theory concepts. We describe a language embedded in Common Lisp, CL-CAT, that allows for succinct expression of such algorithms. Code snippets and examples are presented to help bring this abstract topic closer to practice.

Key Words: Lisp, category theory, domain-specific languages

1 Introduction

Category theory is a relatively young branch of mathematics that has been increasingly used in computer science as a modeling tool [4]. Computational category theory (CCT), on the other hand, is a branch of computer science devoted to the study of algorithms which can be stated in terms of category theory concepts [1]. However, category theory already has applications beyond computer science [11, 12], hence the motivation for using CCT in other domains.

A domain-specific embedded language (DSEL) allows to express algorithms of a particular domain more clearly than a general-purpose language, at the same time reusing the infrastructure and tools of the host language [5]. In Lisp, macros and higher-order functions are the most frequently used means for building DSELs [6]. Some DSELs are called libraries or frameworks despite their use to express computation, which is the purpose of a programming language.

In this paper, we describe a CCT DSEL embedded in Common Lisp, named CL-CAT, that has been designed around algorithms presented in [1]. Thanks to its lending support to mixing object-oriented and functional programming paradigms, CLOS [2, 7] is the main ingredient of CL-CAT: class inheritances and precedences are used for CCT entities, and method combinations and multi-methods simplify the expression of certain function computations.

The next section mentions similar software known to us. The description of the design and implementation, and examples of CL-CAT follow in Sections 3 and 4. Basic knowledge of Common Lisp, CLOS and category theory is required. The exposition is informal, hoping to strike the intuition of a software engineer. We close with hindsight remarks.

2 Related Work

The CCT implementation of [1] uses SML, a general-purpose functional language, and is backed by informal proofs. CL-CAT builds upon its approach and emphasizes the practical side, conceptual integrity and reuse.¹ A survey of formalizations of category theory, such as in proof assistants, is given in [3].

SpecwareTM is a commercial tool that supports the modular construction of formal specifications and their refinement into executable code, based on category theory, sheaf theory, algebraic specification and general logics. It has been developed [13] on top of a CCT layer.

In [14], it is shown how Haskell monads can be composed by computing the coproduct of term representations of their computational effects. This is an elaborate CCT algorithm based on term algebras, the interleaving of induced term *layers*, and quotients of data types. Its approach resembles that of the witness-based unification-as-coequalizer algorithm of [1].

3 Design and Implementation

We give in the sequel the code snippets from the CL-CAT implementation to help explain the most important parts of the design.

3.1 Basic Protocol

In mathematical texts, a *category* is traditionally defined [8, 4] as a structure comprising (i) a collection of *objects*, (ii) a collection of *arrows*, (iii) operations *source* and *target* that each assign an object to an arrow, (iv) operation *identity* that assigns an arrow to an object for which both its source and target are that object, and (v) operation *composition* that assigns to a pair of arrows (g, f) , such that the *target*(f) *equals* *source*(g), their composite arrow gf , such that *source*(gf) = *source*(f) and *target*(gf) = *target*(g). The axioms, which must be satisfied by all the objects and arrows of the category, are (1) *identity/unit law*, that the composition of an arrow with the identity arrow of its source or target *equals* the former arrow, (2) *associative law*, that the order of two compositions does not matter, i.e., the resulting arrows are *equal*.

In practice, the “=” used above means identity/sameness, whereas the meaning of “equals” has to be worked out: it may also be the identity, but its context is often the computation/creation of *new* entities.

In CL-CAT, categories are defined by methods of four generic functions, named after the operations defined above:

¹ It should be noted that some code in [1] expressly avoids genericity due to overhead, even though it is considered desirable in general.

```
(defgeneric source (arrow cat))
(defgeneric target (arrow cat))
(defgeneric id (obj cat))
(defgeneric compo (arrow-g arrow-f cat))
```

The identity and associative laws are not enforced but assumed. The `cat` parameter is introduced in each generic function in order to “free” the other parameters from fictitious dependence on it; this design decision reduces the need for copying and supports nicely some CCT algorithms. Whenever unclear in the sequel, keep in mind that it is a complete and consistent set of methods for the above protocol that defines a particular category, not only the `cat` parameter.

Generic object and arrow classes contain slots for read-only contents, `cobj` and `carr`, respectively. The types of these contents are defined for each particular category; for example, in the **FinSet** category of finite sets, `cobj` contains a finite set and `carr` a total function between two finite sets.

```
(defclass obj ()
  ((cobj :initarg :cobj :reader cobj)))
(defun make-obj (c-des cobj)
  (make-instance c-des :cobj cobj))
(defclass arrow ()
  ((carr :initarg :carr :reader carr)))
(defun make-arrow (c-des so to carr cat &rest keys &key &allow-other-keys)
  (add-arrow (apply #'make-instance c-des :carr carr keys) so to cat))
```

Arrow constructor `make-arrow` associates each arrow with a given category object, for bookkeeping purposes.² This is the `cat` parameter in the basic functional protocol. An arrow may be associated with more than one category via function `add-arrow`. There are `:around` methods for `source` and `target` that use this bookkeeping information if present.

In some computations, object and/or arrow equality may be needed³ to implement the meaning of the above “equals” relations:

```
(defgeneric equalc (x y cat))
```

which has the following predefined methods and can further be specialized for a particular category as intensional or extensional. On composite arrows sharing the source and the target, `equalc` coincides with path commutativity.

```
(defmethod equalc :around ((x obj) (y obj) (c cat))
  (or (eq x y) (eq (cobj x) (cobj y)) (call-next-method)))
(defmethod equalc :around ((f arrow) (g arrow) (c cat))
  (and (equalc (source f c) (source g c) c)
        (equalc (target f c) (target g c) c)
        (or (eq f g) (eq (carr f) (carr g)) (call-next-method))))
(defmethod equalc (x y c) nil)
```

It is also useful to abstract out the arrow application:

² It could be optimized wrt. `c-des` but for the moment, we aim at flexibility.

³ It has to be defined and decidable, which may be a problem for objects. Equality should not be confused with isomorphism.

```
(defgeneric arrow-app (a e c))
(defgeneric arrow-range (a c))
(defgeneric arrow-map (a c))
```

The first generic function computes the *point* of the target of **a** that corresponds to **e** in **c**, the second computes the set of such points for the whole source of **a**, and the third returns the set of pairs of such points.

Finally, we add duality, in the arrow-reversing sense, to the basic protocol:

```
(defgeneric dual (x))
```

which assumes that all necessary information is reachable through the single parameter **x**. There is an `:around` method for `dual` that memoizes the relation between dual entities. The first primary method of `dual` is for categories. Their class contains bookkeeping slots, some of which will be explained in the following examples. Macro `with-dual-restart` invokes `call-next-method` and if it fails,⁴ it evaluates its body instead, to obtain the result via duality. The elided parts below represent the definition of the remaining methods and slots of **c** and **d**.

```
(defclass cat ()
  ((obj-type :initarg :obj-type :reader obj-type)
   (arrow-type :initarg :arrow-type :reader arrow-type)
   (objs :initarg :objs :accessor objs)
   (arrs :initarg :arrs :accessor arrs)
   (arht :accessor arht :initform (make-hash-table :test #'eq))
   (dual-type :initarg :dual-type :accessor dual-type)))
(defun make-cat (c-des obj-type arrow-type &key
  (objs nil supplied-objs-p)
  (arrs nil supplied-arrs-p)
  (dual-type nil supplied-dual-type-p))
  (let ((c (make-instance c-des :obj-type obj-type :arrow-type arrow-type)))
    (when supplied-objs-p (setf (objs c) objs))
    (when supplied-arrs-p (setf (arrs c) arrs))
    (when supplied-dual-type-p (setf (dual-type c) dual-type))
    c))
(defmethod dual ((c cat))
  (let ((d (make-cat (dual-type c) (obj-type c) (arrow-type c))))
    (defmethod source :around ((a arrow) (cat (eql d)))
      (with-dual-restart (target a c)))
    (defmethod source :around ((a arrow) (cat (eql c)))
      (with-dual-restart (target a d)))
    ...
    (defmethod compo ((g arrow) (f arrow) (cat (eql d)))
      (compo f g c))
    ...
    d))
```

It is important to note that, for example, while it is possible to compose two arrows in a category dual to that in which they are created, it is an error to call `arrow-range` on the resulting arrow having the dual category object as an argument. This is because the arrow is flipped but the `carr` cannot be dualized (in general).

⁴ This is done using default primary methods that signal a condition handled by the macro.

3.2 Basic Computations

An entity X , such as an object or an arrow with some structure, computed in CCT may have the *universal property*, or *universality*, meaning that for every other relevant entity, a proof can be constructed that X is distinguished (relative to all these entities). This is implemented via a mixin class `universality` and a generic function `construct`.

```
(defclass universality ()
  ((univ :initarg :univ :accessor univ)))
(defgeneric construct (u &rest args))
(defmethod construct ((u universality) &rest args)
  (apply (univ u) args))
```

A simple example is the initial object:

```
(defclass initial-obj (obj universality) ())
```

for which a method of generic function `compute-initial-obj` binds the slot `univ` of an `initial-obj` X to a function such that `(construct X O)` creates a unique arrow from X to O . Thus for all objects O in the same category as X , even for another initial object, this arrow is a proof that X is initial.

To describe a more interesting example, the colimit, we need to introduce the *functor* first. A functor maps each object in category C_1 to an object in category C_2 , and each arrow in C_1 to an arrow in C_2 , such that these maps commute with all related arrows in C_1 and C_2 . The functors can be thought of as arrows in the category of small categories `Cat`, represented by instance `*cat-cat*` of class `cat-cat`. An as example of the change of perspective, frequent in category theory, the source and target of a functor are instances of a `cat-obj` subclass, whose `cobj` contains an instance of a `cat` subclass.

```
(defclass cat-obj (obj) ())
(defclass functor (arrow) ())
(defclass cat-cat (cat) ())
(defparameter *cat-cat* (make-cat 'cat-cat 'cat-obj 'functor))
```

The `carr` of a functor is thus implemented as a cons of two functions: one for objects and the other for arrows; it is up to the designer to ensure that all the commutativity requirements are satisfied. We introduce `functor-app` and its basic methods.

```
(defgeneric functor-app (f o/a))
(defmethod functor-app ((f functor) (o obj))
  (funcall (car (carr f)) o))
(defmethod functor-app ((f functor) (a arrow))
  (funcall (cdr (carr f)) a))
(defmethod compo ((g functor) (f functor) (c cat-cat))
  (make-arrow
   'functor (source f c) (target g c)
   (cons (lambda (o) (functor-app g (functor-app f o)))
         (lambda (a) (functor-app g (functor-app f a))))))
c))
```

A diagram is defined as a functor from an *index category* which, composed with another functor, gives another diagram. It is implemented as a subclass of `functor`, `diagram`, and has a `compo` method similar to that for functors. The index category, implemented using class `abs-cat`, can be thought of as a graph, with nodes as labeled objects and edges as labeled arrows, kept in the `objs` and `arrs` slots, respectively. Algorithms which work directly with index categories, such as colimit object and free algebra computations, traverse these collections.

Next, we need to introduce the *cocone*, an object with additional structure, analogous to the upper bound: a family of arrows having it as their target in C and commuting with all related arrows in C . The mental picture of these arrows and related objects is an index category with a diagram mapping it to the cocone object “over” C . This already complex situation could be further generalized, but by optimization, we only implement the picture as a diagram stored in slot `base` of an `obj` subclass. Slot `sides` contains a function that maps the source of an arrow in the index category to the corresponding arrow in C . The inherited slot `cobj` has the same type as that of any other object in C . The `carr` of a `cocone-arrow`, however, is an arrow in C .

```
(defclass conic-obj (obj)
  ((base :initarg :base :reader base)
   (sides :initarg :sides :reader sides)))
(defclass conic-arrow (arrow) ())
(defun side (c n) (funcall (sides c) n))
(defclass cocone (conic-obj) ())
(defun make-cocone (coapex base sides)
  (make-instance
   'cocone :cobj (cobj coapex) :base base :sides sides))
(defclass cocone-arrow (conic-arrow) ())
```

The colimit object is a generalization of entities such as the initial object in a *cocomplete* category C .⁵ Analogous to a least upper bound, it is computed as a “universal completion” over cocone objects, and its class is `colimit-cocone`.⁶

```
(defclass colimit-cocone (cocone universality) ())
(defun make-colimit-cocone (cocone univ)
  (make-instance
   'colimit-cocone :cobj (cobj cocone) :base (base cocone)
   :sides (sides cocone) :univ univ))
```

The `functor-app` methods specialized on the `conic-obj` and `conic-arrow`, together with methods on `compo` and `dual`, implement (co)limit-preserving (co)-continuous functors, inheriting the basic behavior via `call-next-method`.

For computing universal completions, two layers of functional protocols are:

```
(defgeneric compute-colimit (d c))
(defgeneric compute-limit (d c))
```

⁵ A cocomplete category is one that has colimits on all diagrams. In CCT, this means that they can be computed.

⁶ Notice that `univ` parameter of `make-colimit-cocone` pertains to `cocone` parameter, whereas we create a new object to avoid side-effects. Even though `equalc` returns true on the two objects, this is a potential issue.

```
(defgeneric compute-initial-obj (o c))
(defgeneric compute-coproduct (lo ro c))
(defgeneric compute-coequalizer (f g c))
...
```

When the lower-layer methods can be implemented by reusing existing code, going in the other direction is allowed. For example, the default method of `compute-coproduct` below uses `compute-colimit`. The most general method of `compute-colimit` is shown first, using `compute-colimit*`, which in turn uses the lower protocol layer for base cases of a structural recursion. The class names contain `io` when a `compute-initial-obj` method is defined, `cp` when `compute-coproduct` is defined, etc. By theorems, an `io-cp-ce` category inherits from mixin class `cocomplete-cat`, and a `to-pr-eq` category from `complete-cat`.

```
(defmethod compute-colimit ((d diagram) (cat io-cp-ce-cat))
  (compute-colimit* d cat d))
```

Function `cp-diagram` creates a diagram from an index category containing two objects⁷ and no arrows, to `c`. The `p-arrow` and `q-arrow` are names used for injections and projections. Instead of `defun`, `def-memoized-fun` memoizes `compute-cp-via-colimit` in order to allow for subdividing client code which depends on the identity: when using the `equalc` is not desired or possible.⁸

```
(defclass coproduct (obj universality)
  ((p-arrow :initarg :p-arrow :reader p-arrow)
   (q-arrow :initarg :q-arrow :reader q-arrow)))
(defmethod compute-coproduct ((lo obj) (ro obj) (c cocomplete-cat))
  (compute-cp-via-colimit lo ro c))
(def-memoized-fun +memo+ compute-cp-via-colimit (a b c)
  (let* ((d (cp-diagram a b c))
         (cc (compute-colimit d c)))
    (make-instance
     'coproduct :cobj (cobj cc)
     :p-arrow (side cc *cp-lo*)
     :q-arrow (side cc *cp-ro*)
     :univ (lambda (o a1 a2)
             (let ((c1 (make-cocone
                       o d
                       (lambda (x)
                        (ecase (cobj x) (cp-lo a1) (cp-ro a2))))))
               (carr (construct cc c1))))))))))
```

Using the `dual` method for functors, `pr-diagram` creates a product diagram:

```
(defun pr-diagram (a b c) (dual (cp-diagram a b (dual c))))
```

The category of finite sets, **FinSet**, is bicomplete⁹ and in CL-CAT is named `fin-set-cat`. Using the naming convention above, its class hierarchy is:

⁷ Since the same index category can be used as the source of all coproduct diagrams, by optimization we use its fixed objects, `*cp-lo*` and `*cp-ro*`, to construct a coproduct object. For diagrams induced by a set of objects and a set of arrows, function `make-diagram` is provided.

⁸ The `+memo+` is an instance of key situation, using `equal` for the argument list, from the generic hash-table implementation (see code referred to in [9]).

⁹ Both cocomplete and complete, i.e., has all colimits and all limits.

```

(defclass fin-set-cat (cat) ())
(defclass io-cp-ce-fin-set-cat (fin-set-cat io-cp-ce-cat) ())
(defclass to-pr-eq-fin-set-cat (fin-set-cat to-pr-eq-cat) ())
(defclass bicomplete-cat (cocomplete-cat complete-cat) ())
(defclass io-cp-ce-to-pr-eq-fin-set-cat
  (io-cp-ce-fin-set-cat to-pr-eq-fin-set-cat bicomplete-cat) ())

```

Using the method `compute-colimit` on any other `io-cp-ce` category, and method `dual` on a `to-pr-eq` category, method `compute-limit` can be defined to reuse the code for computing a colimit object.

```

(defmethod dual ((c to-pr-eq-cat))
  (let ((dc (call-next-method)))
    (defmethod compute-initial-obj ((o obj) (cat (eql dc)))
      (if *limit-via-dual-colimit*
          (compute-terminal-obj o (dual dc))
          (call-next-method)))
      ...
    dc))
(defmethod compute-limit ((d diagram) (c to-pr-eq-cat))
  (let ((*limit-via-dual-colimit* t)
        (dual (compute-colimit (dual d) (dual c)))))

```

The variable `*limit-via-dual-colimit*` controls the context, in the sense of [10]: the colimit computation is used, but in a context where only limit objects are to be constructed. Methods `compute-pushout` and `compute-pullback` are also defined on cocomplete and complete categories, respectively.

4 Examples

We present in this section three examples, which include computations of gradually increasing complexity.

4.1 Product and Coproduct

For a complete category represented by an instance of class `to-pr-eq-fin-set-cat`, the product of two objects below:

```

(defparameter *fsc-ccat*
  (make-cat 'to-pr-eq-fin-set-cat 'fin-set-obj 'fin-set-arrow))
(defparameter *fsc-a* (make-obj 'fin-set-obj '(a b)))
(defparameter *fsc-b* (make-obj 'fin-set-obj '(c d)))

```

with 2-tuples as cones and sets as lists, pretty-printed looks like:

```

CAT-USER> (compute-product *fsc-a* *fsc-b* *fsc-ccat*)
#<PRODUCT ((A . C) (A . D) (B . C) (B . D))>
CAT-USER> (arrow-app (p-arrow *) '(A . C) *fsc-ccat*)
A

```

This is useful for debugging,¹⁰ even though the above presentation of the `cobj` value does not always match the intuition, which is the canonical Cartesian product. This is because the product object is unique up to isomorphism.

¹⁰ Optionally, for debugging purposes, `print-object` methods can also print unique object identifiers for direct access to CLOS objects that have been printed out.

Similarly, given an instance of class `io-cp-ce-fin-set-cat`:

```
(defparameter *fsc-c2cat*
  (make-cat 'io-cp-ce-fin-set-cat 'fin-set-obj 'fin-set-arrow))
```

the coproduct of the two objects above looks like:

```
CAT-USER> (compute-coproduct *fsc-a* *fsc-b* *fsc-c2cat*)
#<COPRODUCT (^A ^B ^C ^D)>
CAT-USER> (arrow-range (q-arrow *) *fsc-c2cat*)
(^C ^D)
```

where the caret and tilde represents the “left” and the “right” tag of the disjoint union, respectively, consed up with the points but handled by the pretty-printer.

4.2 Relation Composition (Equijoin)

The exposition in [1] is recast in CL-CAT using a mixin `rel-cat` category class, added to the complete `FinSet` category implementation, which partially defines a category whose arrows of class `rel-arrow` contain *span* (multirelation, finite set) objects as *carr*. The composition of two `rel-arrow`s contains a new span that is computed using the pullback (also called fibered product) over the spans of the two `rel-arrow`s; the base case is a pullback of two unique `fin-set-arrows` to the terminal object (denoted by `1`), which degenerates to a product. In Figure 1, the circular nodes are regular `fin-set-obj` objects, the regular arrows are `fin-set-arrows`, the rectangular nodes are span objects of the thick `rel-arrow`s; the dotted gray arrows and the universalities are disposed of upon composition.

Figure 1: Relation composition using pullbacks, as `rel-arrow` composition

```
(defclass rel-cat (cat) ())
(defclass rel-arrow (arrow) ())
(defclass span (fin-set-obj)
  ((p-arrow :initarg :p-arrow :reader p-arrow)
   (q-arrow :initarg :q-arrow :reader q-arrow)))
(defmethod compo ((g rel-arrow) (f rel-arrow) (c rel-cat))
  (let ((pb (compute-pullback
             (q-arrow (carr f)) (p-arrow (carr g)) c)))
    (make-arrow
     'rel-arrow (source f c) (target g c)
     (make-instance
```

```

      'span :cobj (cobj pb)
      :p-arrow (compo (p-arrow (carr f)) (p-arrow pb) c)
      :q-arrow (compo (q-arrow (carr g)) (q-arrow pb) c)
    c)))
(defun rel-tuples (rel-arrow rel-cat)
  (let ((sp (carr rel-arrow)))
    (remove-duplicates
     (mapcar (lambda (e)
              (cons (arrow-app (p-arrow sp) e rel-cat)
                    (arrow-app (q-arrow sp) e rel-cat)))
            (cobj sp))
     :test 'equal)))

```

The computation of the join of two relations over three `fin-set-obj` objects is then the composition of `rel-arrows`. Below, pairs are conses and sets are lists.

```

(defclass fsc-cat (rel-cat to-pr-eq-fin-set-cat) ())
(defclass fsc-obj (fin-set-obj) ())
(defclass fsc-arrow (rel-arrow) ())
(defclass fscd-cat (rel-cat io-cp-ce-fin-set-cat) ())
(defparameter *fsc*
  (make-cat 'fsc-cat 'fsc-obj 'fsc-arrow :dual-type 'fscd-cat))
(defparameter *fsc-a* (make-obj 'fsc-obj '(1 2)))
(defparameter *fsc-b* (make-obj 'fsc-obj '(3 4 5)))
(defparameter *fsc-c* (make-obj 'fsc-obj '(6 7)))
(defparameter *fsc-r*
  (let ((o (make-obj 'fsc-obj '((1 . 3) (2 . 3) (2 . 4)))))
    (make-arrow
     'rel-arrow *fsc-a* *fsc-b*
     (make-instance
      'span :cobj (cobj o)
      :p-arrow (make-arrow 'fin-set-arrow o *fsc-a* #'car *fsc*)
      :q-arrow (make-arrow 'fin-set-arrow o *fsc-b* #'cdr *fsc*))
     *fsc*)))
(defparameter *fsc-s*
  (let ((o (make-obj 'fsc-obj '((3 . 6) (4 . 6) (4 . 7) (5 . 6)))))
    (make-arrow
     'rel-arrow *fsc-b* *fsc-c*
     (make-instance
      'span :cobj (cobj o)
      :p-arrow (make-arrow 'fin-set-arrow o *fsc-b* #'car *fsc*)
      :q-arrow (make-arrow 'fin-set-arrow o *fsc-c* #'cdr *fsc*))
     *fsc*)))

```

The class of the category dual to `*fsc*`, `fscd-cat`, is explicitly defined in order to reuse its `compute-colimit` for the pullbacks. The composition is then:

```

CAT-USER> (compo *fsc-s* *fsc-r* *fsc*)
#<REL-ARROW #<SPAN ((3 (1 . 3) (3 . 6) . T) (3 (2 . 3) (3 . 6) . T)
                  (4 (2 . 4) (4 . 6) . T) (4 (2 . 4) (4 . 7) . T))>>
CAT-USER> (rel-tuples * *fsc*)
((1 . 6) (2 . 6) (2 . 7))

```

The `T` comes from products with the terminal object, which is a singleton set `{T}`, because the generic limit computation is used that creates a non-canonical `cobj` value. It is “removed” by the `p-arrow` and the `q-arrow` of the span object, and function `rel-tuples` obtains the set of 2-tuples from it.¹¹

¹¹ Conses and simple Lisp objects are used for `fin-set` elements, the built-in `equal` for element equality, and a function `set-equal` for finite set equality.

It is further possible to compute the intersection `rel-arrow` over a pair of parallel `rel-arrows` by computing the limit on a diagram induced by the related `fin-set` arrows in `*fsc*`, using the function `make-diagram`. Then similarly, the union `rel-arrow` using the universality of the pushout¹² of `fin-set` arrows from the limit to the pair's `carrs`. Notice how the `compo` multimethod facilitates the implementation of these algorithms, which deal with two categories at the same time, using a single CLOS object, `*fsc*`.

4.3 Three-Valued Logic Topos

We have seen the `fin-set` category, with a minimum of structure. The category of graphs has more structure in the form of imposed constraints such as that an edge has a source and a target. It can be implemented using a parameterized *comma* category, an instance of class `comma-cat`. The parameters are two functors, L and R , that share the target category, and objects in a comma category (L, R) are 3-tuples of objects of the two source categories and a corresponding arrow in the target category; see Figure 2 (left). In the case of finite graphs, the source categories are the same instance of `fin-set`: objects are edge and node sets, respectively; and arrows are functions from the edge sets to (source, target) node-pair sets, both associated with the `fin-set` target category.

A little simpler use of the comma category can help implement the three-valued logic on a topos. First, we describe the implementation of a topos, which is a bicomplete category with an *exponential* and a *subobject classifier*. We do not use an exponential object in the example, so a bicomplete category with a subobject classifier suffices. The subobject classifier Ω , an object with: the logical values, a constant `t-arrow` from the terminal object selecting T , and a universality, is defined below.

```
(defclass subobj-classifier (obj universality)
  ((t-arrow :initarg :t-arrow :reader t-arrow)))
(defgeneric truth-carr (cat))
(defgeneric compute-truth-arrow (to omega to-cat))
(defgeneric chi-carr (m cat))
(defgeneric compute-chi-arrow (m omega to-cat))
(def-memoized-fun +memo+ compute-subobj-classifier (to omega to-cat)
  (make-instance
   'subobj-classifier :cobj (cobj omega)
   :t-arrow (compute-truth-arrow to omega to-cat)
   :univ (lambda (m) (compute-chi-arrow m omega to-cat))))
```

The *chi* stands for the characteristic arrow, which maps/classifies a point of the target of a monic arrow m to a point in Ω iff it satisfies a criterion of being in the corresponding subobject of the target. It is just a mnemonic for `construct`.

¹² For this, the complete category represented by `fsc-cat` must be extended to a bicomplete category. Note that limits, even in a bicomplete category, must be computed via colimits in their dual category, in order to reuse code.

In the familiar case of `fin-set`, the monic `m` may be a set inclusion (its source is a subset of its target, so it determines a subobject of the target), and each element in the range of `m` is mapped by the characteristic arrow to `T` in Ω . The following function creates an arrow from the source of `m`, `o`, to Ω (`sc`) such that it maps each element of `o` to `T` and, at the same time, commutes with the composition of `m` with its characteristic arrow in `c`.¹³

```
(defun true (o sc c)
  (let ((to (compute-terminal-obj *dummy-obj* c)))
    (compo (t-arrow sc) (construct to o) c)))
```

Methods on the generic `compute-*-arrow` functions above are defined for `fin-set` and `comma-cat`. Methods for the other two are defined on demand.

For the internal logic, we need the terminal object and Ω . Constants are arrows from the terminal object to Ω , unary connectives from Ω to Ω , and binary connectives from $\Omega \times \Omega$ to Ω . For example, as explained in [15], \vee (`top-or`) is defined, given a subobject classifier `sc` and a category `c`, using both colimit and limit computations in `c`. The `epi-mono-factorize` returns a (*mono . epi*).

```
(def-memoized-fun +memo+ top-or (sc c)
  (let* ((cp (compute-coproduct sc sc c))
        (pr (compute-product sc sc c))
        (st (true sc sc c))
        (si (id sc c))
        (p1 (construct pr sc si st))
        (p2 (construct pr sc st si))
        (m (construct cp pr p1 p2)))
    (chi sc (car (epi-mono-factorize m c)))))
```

Finally, we give the example, then explain further details.

```
(defclass fs-obj (fin-set-obj) ())
(defclass fs-arrow (fin-set-arrow) ())
(defclass fs-cat (io-cp-ce-to-pr-eq-fin-set-cat)
  () (:default-initargs :dual-type 'fsd-cat))
(defclass fsd-cat (io-cp-ce-to-pr-eq-fin-set-cat)
  () (:default-initargs :dual-type 'fs-cat))
(defparameter *fsc* (make-cat 'fs-cat 'fs-obj 'fs-arrow))
(defparameter *l* (make-cocontinuous-functor-via-identity *fsc*))
(defparameter *r* (make-continuous-functor-via-identity *fsc*))
(defclass top-cat (bicomplete-comma-cat)
  () (:default-initargs :dual-type 'topd-cat))
(defclass topd-cat (bicomplete-comma-cat)
  () (:default-initargs :dual-type 'top-cat))
(defparameter *fcc* (make-comma-cat 'top-cat *l* *r*))
(defparameter *src* (make-obj 'fs-obj '(f * t)))
(defparameter *tgt* (make-obj 'fs-obj '(f t)))
(defparameter *to* (compute-terminal-obj *dummy-obj* *fcc*))
(defparameter *omega*
  (make-comma-obj
   *src*
   (make-arrow
    'fs-arrow (functor-app *l* *src*) (functor-app *r* *tgt*)
    (lambda (e) (ecase e (f 'f) (* t) (t t))) *fsc*)
   *tgt*))
(defparameter *sc* (compute-subobj-classifier *to* *omega* *fcc*))
```

¹³ The `*dummy-obj*` is used and ignored when we want the terminal object to be unique.

The `*l*` and `*r*` are identity functors that preserve colimits and limits, respectively. This is needed by the `compute-colimit` method on `*fcc*`, which is computed via `compute-colimit` on the source categories. The `compute-limit` method on `*fcc*` uses duality, two more comma categories and an isomorphism.

```
(defmethod compute-limit ((d diagram) (c complete-comma-cat))
  (let* ((idc (iso-dual-comma-cat c))
        (i (make-dual-comma-isomorphism c))
        (*limit-via-dual-colimit* t))
    (limit-via-iso-duality d i idc)))
```

The function `limit-via-iso-duality` implements a generic construction: it first computes the colimit in `idc`, then creates a cocontinuous functor from `i`,¹⁴ uses the two to construct the colimit in the dual of `c`, and finally applies to it the `dual` method for colimit cocones. The variable `*limit-via-dual-colimit*` is bound to `T` in order to construct the resulting limit object using limit objects in the (dual of `*fsc*`) `fin-set` category while reusing the colimit computation.

Figure 2: Two comma objects and a comma arrow (h_s, h_t) between them: (left) in general, and (right) for the topos. The rectangles in the middle must commute.

The objects of `*fcc*` are 3-tuples that boil down to just `fin-set` arrows, as shown in Figure 2. The additional structure of this comma category can be seen in its arrows: they are commuting squares which, when Ω is the source and/or target, factor through `*omega*`'s `fin-set` arrow. Therefore, all the constants and the connectives of the topos must be consistent with this function from the 3-valued to the 2-valued set.

Two other parameters of the topos are `truth-carr` and `chi-carr` below. The 3-value part of the `chi-carr` returns `*` for those elements that are in a subset according to the 2-valued logic but not according to the 3-valued logic. The constituent `fin-set` categories of a comma category are kept in a list stored in its `obj-type`, and the two functors in its `arrow-type`.

¹⁴ For `c` being (L, R) , `idc` is $(dual(R), dual(L))$ and `i` is an isomorphism between `idc` and the dual of `c`.

```

(defmethod truth-carr ((c top-cat))
  (cons (constant-fn t) (constant-fn t)))
(defun inv-range (a cda cdb c)
  (let ((s (cobj (source a c))))
    (set-difference
      (loop for x in s
            when (member (arrow-app a x c) cdb :test 'equal)
              collect x)
      cda
      :test 'equal)))
(defmethod chi-carr ((m arrow) (c top-cat))
  (let* ((cats (obj-type c))
         (ac (car cats))
         (bc (cadr cats))
         (cc (caddr cats))
         (mc (carr m))
         (mt (target m c))
         (cda (arrow-range (car mc) ac))
         (cdb (arrow-range (cdr mc) bc))
         (cdc (inv-range (cadr (cobj mt)) cda cdb cc)))
    (cons
      (lambda (z)
        (if (member z cda :test 'equal)
            t
            (if (member z cdc :test 'equal) '* 'f)))
      (lambda (z) (if (member z cdb :test 'equal) t 'f))))))

```

Finally, we can compute the 3-valued and 2-valued “truth tables”¹⁵ for the above arrow `top-or`. The method `arrow-map` on a `comma-arrow` returns a `cons` of the same generic function applied on its constituent arrows.

```

CAT-USER> (arrow-map (top-or *sc* *fcc*) *fcc*)
(((F F . T) . F) ((F * . T) . *) ((F T . T) . T) ((* F . T) . *)
 ((* * . T) . *) ((* T . T) . T) ((T F . T) . T) ((T * . T) . T)
 ((T T . T) . T))
((F F . T) . F) ((F T . T) . T) ((T F . T) . T) ((T T . T) . T))

```

5 Conclusion

The work on CL-CAT has been a hobby project with the goal to deepen the understanding of category theory and CCT by coding them in the familiar language. There have been numerous iterations involving extension and refactorization. Whereas the basic CCT is supported at least as much as in [1],¹⁶ without the need for auxiliary data structures such as graphs, many open questions remain in general. The contribution of CL-CAT is mainly a reduced set of CLOS protocols and other constructs that facilitate the experimentation with category-theoretic concepts and CCT algorithms.

Although the concrete syntax is considered important for a DSEL, we have abode by Lisp style guidelines, e.g., not used a macro when a function would

¹⁵ Something similar to the function `rel-tuples` is needed for beautification.

¹⁶ This includes functor and product categories, adjunctions, term algebra, with the connected components, transitive closure and unification algorithms.

suffice. This helps a DSEL to be better embedded in the host language and benefit from existing tools, e.g. for code coverage.

One of the most difficult parts has been the arrow flipping, such as in `limit-via-iso-duality`, related to the approach to duality, which is a novelty of CL-CAT. Further refinement is needed to ensure that duality is propagated in compound objects, even if unused. Equality on objects and points needs more work, perhaps by extending `equalc` and integrating it with the generalized hash-tables. Similarly for the mapping of points, which generalize to diagrams (maps from “map-separating objects” [8]). For the functional CLOS protocols used, only the primary `around/call-next-method` portion of the standard method combination seem appropriate for the functional nature of CCT.

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